

Production of Aluminium Tri-hydroxides from Secondary Bauxite Materials

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Abstract

The study is currently evaluating the hydrometallurgical aspects of the Pedersen process as an alternative route to the Bayer process for producing metallurgical grade alumina. The Pedersen process is potentially applicable on lower grade ores and a wider variety of bauxite materials. The test material used was slag which was obtained through the smelter-reduction of a mixture of bauxite residue (red mud) and a calcite-rich bauxite beneficiation by-product. The process was evaluated at lab-scale using a 1 L jacketed glass reactor.

Six experimental programmes were conducted each consisting of a leaching, desilication and precipitation test. Samples of the slag were leached with Na_2CO_3 solution at 90 °C. The tests varied in Na_2CO_3 concentration and leaching time. Additionally, different approaches to leaching involving mechanical treatment of the leached slag and re-leaching using either fresh or recycled solution were also explored. The desilication step was carried out by treating the leachate solution with powdered CaO at 70°C varying the amounts used. Finally, the desilicated solution was sparged with a gas mixture of equal parts Ar and CO_2 after which the precipitate was allowed to age in the solution for a period of time. The carbonation and aging temperatures and times were varied. As much as 73 % of the Al has been leached from the slag. The desilication process has shown to remove 88 % of the Si. The precipitation process produced a product composed entirely of the aluminium tri-hydroxides. It was observed that the unwanted phase of dawsonite in the final product can perhaps be avoided by using a solution of Na_2CO_3 with concentrations not more than 60 g/l. Furthermore, the carbonation and aging temperatures should not exceed 30 °C.

1 Introduction

From 1928 a plant working on the basis of the Pedersen process was operated in Høyanger, Norway for over 40 years [1]. The plant operated at a production capacity of 17 000 tpa of alumina and some 4000 tpa of pig iron was also produced mostly from Greek bauxite. By 1969 the Pedersen process was no longer in use due to economic reasons. However, in 2017 a consortium under the ENSUREAL project began investigating a revival of the Pedersen process as an alternative to the Bayer process in the production of metallurgical grade alumina [2].

The Pedersen process uses pyrometallurgy and hydrometallurgy to extract alumina from bauxite ores. The alumina production industry is currently completely dominated by the Bayer process. However, the Bayer process has its challenges specifically the production of red mud as a by-product which is a significant environmental hazard. Red mud, also referred to as bauxite residue, is a fine sludge material that is highly alkaline, mostly composed of Fe_2O_3 and is voluminous. In contrast the Pedersen process produces by-products that can be used in other industries making it a zero-waste process. Additionally, it can potentially be applied to a wider range of materials than the Bayer process specifically lower grade bauxite materials [3].

In the Pedersen process the bauxite ore once crushed and milled is mixed with coke / carbon and lime to be smelted at temperatures in excess of 1500 °C. This produces a slag mostly composed of calcium-aluminate minerals and pig iron. These two products are easily physically separable, and the pig iron may be further processed to cast iron. The slag is then milled and leached with Na_2CO_3 solution as per the following equations:

The Al is leached leaving a solid residue composed mostly of CaCO_3 , this is referred to as grey mud. Unlike red mud, grey mud is environmentally benign and can potentially be used in the cement or fertilizer industry. The leach liquor is then sparged with CO_2 gas to precipitate Al tri-hydroxides (equation 3). These are calcined to produce alumina.

A basic flowsheet of the process can be seen in figure 1 below.

The current study is aiming to evaluate the feasibility of using the Pedersen process on secondary bauxite materials. More specifically a slag composed of a mixture of red mud (bauxite residue) and a calcite-rich bauxite beneficiation by-product. The study will focus on the hydrometallurgical part of the Pedersen process being the leaching of the slag, the desilication of the leach liquor and finally the precipitation of hydrated alumina from the desilicated solution.

Figure 1: Basic Flowsheet of Pedersen Process

Literature on detailed scientific studies about the process during the time it was in operation are not available due to confidential developments. The available literature are mostly short document patents and test reports [4, 5, 6] which have conflicting process parameters and often a very wide range parameters are reported. More recent studies [3, 7, 8], some within the ENSUREAL, have been used in selecting process parameters for the leaching and precipitation experiments while the desilication process was adapted from Blake et al. [9]. The most notable outcomes from these studies was the observation of the formation of a calcium-containing passivation layer around the slag grains limiting

the extraction of Al during leaching [3]. Further, leaching solutions with a Na_2CO_3 concentration higher than 100 g/l were observed to promote dawsonite $[\text{NaAlCO}_3(\text{OH})_2]$ precipitation over the desired Al tri-hydroxides gibbsite and bayerite [7, 8]. Additionally, it was noted that the precipitation process had to be a combination of carbonation and aging (allowing the precipitate to sit in solution for at least 24 hrs after carbonation) in order to convert boehmite to bayerite and gibbsite [8, 9]. Furthermore, elevated temperatures exceeding 60 °C have been reported to promote gibbsite formation [10, 11].

2 Material

The starting materials for the slag were red mud and bauxite ore by-product with the chemistry detailed in table 1.

Table 1: XRF quantitative analysis of bauxite residue and by-product (wt.-%)

Oxides	Red Mud	By-product	Oxides	Red Mud	By-product
Al_2O_3	22.78	25.33	Na_2O	1.93	–
CaO	8.44	34.49	MnO	0.10	–
TiO_2	5.88	1.24	Cr_2O_3	0.26	0.01
SiO_2	6.35	1.11	P_2O_5	0.19	–
Fe_2O_3	43.59	5.61	NiO	0.07	–
MgO	0.56	–	S	0.15	0.01
V_2O_5	0.30	–	LoI	9.30	32.20

The materials including the lime were calcined at 900 °C for 3 hrs. 3 kg of a mixture in a ratio of red mud (60 %) and a calcite-rich bauxite beneficiation by-product (40 %) was prepared. To this mixture, lime (CaO) in a ratio of 21 wt.-% of the mixture was added. Half of the material was placed in a cylindrical graphite crucible and heated to 1650 °C in an IF75 induction furnace (Inductotherm Europe, Droitwich Spa, UK). Then the remainder of the material was added which resulted in a temperature drop. Some time was allowed for the temperature to reach 1650 °C once again and it was held at that temperature for 40 minutes before the furnace was shut down and allowed to cool overnight. The resulting slag was separated from the pig iron and crushed and screened to produce a bulk sample that was $-75 \mu\text{m}$. The material was then subject to splitting using 2-way rifle splitters and an 8-way Retsch DR rotary splitter to produce sample sizes of 100 g for leaching test work. Smaller sub-samples were obtained for analysis by XRF (table 2) while XRD analysis (table 3) showed the slag contained Al as gehlenite and mayenite. A material balance using the molecular weights of the minerals shows that the Al is more or less equally distributed between the two minerals.

Table 2: XRF quantitative analysis of slag (wt.-%)

Al ₂ O ₃	CaO	SiO ₂	TiO ₂	MgO	Fe	SO ₃
39.6	43.9	6.99	5.84	0.17	1.82	0.18
MnO	Na ₂ O	ZrO ₂	SrO	Cr ₂ O ₃	V ₂ O ₅	P ₂ O ₅
0.06	1.19	0.14	0.06	0.03	< 0.01	< 0.05

Table 3: XRD semi-quantitative analysis of mineral phases in the slag

Minerals	wt.-%
Gehlenite (Ca ₂ Al ₂ SiO ₇)	40
Mayenite (Ca ₁₂ Al ₁₄ O ₃₃)	16
Perovskite (not CaTiO ₃)	21
Larnite (Ca ₂ SiO ₄)	23

3 Methods

3.1 Leaching

Six test programs were conducted using the equipment shown in figure 2. The same reactor was used for all three processes. After each experiment the reactor was thoroughly cleaned in preparation for the next experiment. Each test program commenced with a leaching experiment. The leaching experiments are detailed in table 4. All experiments used 1 l of Na₂CO₃ solution, 100 g of slag material and were conducted at 90°C with rate of agitation of 500 rpm. The slurry was heated and cooled using silicon oil circulated using a circulator thermo-bath and the volume of the reactor was maintained using a water-cooled condenser. For the first test the sample was first leached with solution of concentration 60 g/l then it was recovered, dried and subjected to physical force using a pestle and mortar. The force provided by the pestle and mortar was not expected to grind or break particles but perhaps help remove the passivation layer. Using the same solution used to leach the sample in the first instance, the sample was re-leached with the intention of extracting more Al. For the second test some NaOH was added to determine if its addition would result in less Si dissolved [5, 6]. It was worth investigating this although previous studies have shown the addition of NaOH reduced Al extraction [3]. In the third test the slag sample was leached with solution concentration of 60 g/l for 3 hrs. In the fourth test the sample was leached using a solution concentration of 100 g/l for 1.5 hrs; recovered, dried and mechanically treated with a pestle and mortar then re-leached with the same solution (recycled). In the fifth test the sample was leached with solution concentration of 40 g/l for 1.5 hrs; recovered, dried and mechanically treated with a pestle and mortar then re-leached with fresh solution of 40 g/l concentration. In the sixth test the sample was leached with a solution of concentration 80 g/l for 3 hours. In all cases at the end of the experiments the slurries were vacuum filtered with general purpose filter paper to separate the solid residue (grey mud) and leachate solution. The grey mud was dried overnight at 100°C and analyzed via

XRD to determine the mineral phases and XRF for chemical composition for a material balance. The leachate solution was cooled overnight for the desilication step.

Figure 2: Equipment used for leaching, desilication and precipitation experiments.

3.2 Desilication

The desilication method, adapted from Blake et al. [9], was conducted on the solutions from all tests except for test no 5. A sample of solution was taken at the start and end of the test and vacuum filtered with a 0.2 μm membrane for ICP analysis. All the tests were conducted by adding the leachate solution to powdered CaO in the glass reactor. 14 g of CaO was added to the solutions from test no 1 and 2, while 28 g was added to the solutions from test no 3, 4 and 6. In each test the mixture was heated to 70 °C and agitated at 400 rpm for 2 hrs. At the end of each test the solution was vacuum filtered with general purpose filter paper. The solution was kept and cooled overnight for the precipitation tests. The solid residue was dried at 60 °C for 2 days and analyzed via XRD and XRF.

Table 4: Schedule of leaching experiments

No.	1 st Stage Leach	Intermediate Step	2 nd Stage Leach
1	60 g/l Na ₂ CO ₃ and 1.5 hrs	Grinding with pestle & mortar	Recycled solution from 1 st Stage Leach
2	60 g/l Na ₂ CO ₃ , 4 g NaOH and 1.5 hrs	None	None
3	60 g/l Na ₂ CO ₃ and 3 hrs	None	None
4	100 g/l Na ₂ CO ₃ and 1.5 hrs	Grinding with pestle & mortar	Recycled solution from 1 st Stage Leach
5	40 g/l Na ₂ CO ₃ and 1.5 hrs	Grinding with pestle & mortar	Leach with fresh solution 40 g/l Na ₂ CO ₃
6	80 g/l Na ₂ CO ₃ and 3 hrs	None	None

3.3 Precipitation

The precipitation tests were conducted on all the desilicated solutions as per Table 5. The tests were conducted the day after desilication allowing the solutions to cool overnight. In all the tests the desilicated solutions were sparged with a gas mixture equal parts Ar and CO₂. The gas flow rate was 1.5 slpm and the solution was agitated at a rate of 200 rpm. The solutions were sparged for a certain interval and the mixture (liquid and precipitate) was allowed to age for different periods of time. At the end of the test the mixture was vacuum filtered with general purpose filter paper to recover the precipitate. The precipitate was dried at 60°C for 2 days and samples were taken for XRD, XRF and PSD analysis. Solution samples were taken before and after the test and vacuum filtered with a 0.2 µm membrane for ICP analysis.

Table 5: Schedule of precipitation experiments

No.	Solution from Leach Expt No.	Temp.	P _{CO2}	Rate of Agitation	Duration	Aging
		[°C]	[%]	[rpm]	[hrs]	[days]
1	1	25	50	200	0.5	3
2	2	25	50	200	0.5	3
3	3	50	50	200	1	1
4	4	75	50	200	2	1
5	6	25	50	200	2	1

4 Results and Discussion

4.1 Leaching

The extraction of Al achieved was calculated from a material balance performed by using XRF analysis on the slag and the resulting grey mud (table 6). Despite varying certain process conditions and using different approaches to leaching, the extractions of Al were similar across the six tests. Going into the test programme it was not known to what extent the gehlenite would leach under the conditions of the Pedersen process. The extraction levels in table 6 suggest part of the gehlenite may have leached out. Further, table 7 shows that the amount of gehlenite in the grey mud is much less than in the slag (table 3). However, it should be noted that the mayenite has mostly or completely leached out in all samples and there is a considerable amount of calcite that has formed, and this may account for the reduced amount of gehlenite. Further still the XRD analysis had a few unidentified peaks which overlapped with the gehlenite and mayenite peaks. These may have been unidentified phases of Al which were identified as gehlenite and mayenite. These phases may have been leached accounting for the extraction levels in table 6 and this does suggest that gehlenite is in fact not leachable. However, this is only speculation.

Table 6: Al percentage extraction determined by XRF analysis

Experiment No.	1	2	3	4	5	6
XRF [%]	71.61	68.66	63.69	67.02	72.99	63.71

Table 7: XRD semi-quantitative analysis of the grey mud samples [wt.-%]

Phase	Experiment No.					
	1	2	3	4	5	6
Calcite (CaCO ₃)	56	46	54	66	59	56
Gehlenite	20	24	21	7	16	17
Perovskite	15	17	14	14	17	16
Larnite	7	12	10	5	8	9
Mayenite	1	1	0	0	0	0
Zeolite A (NaAlSiO ₄)	0.5	0	0.5	8	0	2
Bayerite	0.5	0	0	0	0	0

4.2 Desilication

The results (Table 8) show that overall, the desilication step does reduce the concentration of Si in solution. However, there is some inconsistency in the results. The use of an increased amount of CaO (28 g) results in a much lower concentration of Si for experiments 3 and 6 than when 14 g was used in experiments 1 and 2 but not 4. Additionally, there was co-precipitation of Al in all the experiments as seen from the mineral phases produced in table 9. The composition of the desilication products can be seen in

Table 9. The process was adapted but the literature did not indicate the chemistry of the process and future work will focus on understanding this process in more detail.

Table 8: Amounts of Si before and after desilication and % reduction of Si in solution

Experiment No.		1	2	3	4	6
Start	[g/l]	0.2	0.15	0.15	0.31	0.32
End	[g/l]	0.15	0.11	0.02	0.23	0.04
Reduction	%	25	27	87	26	88

Table 9: XRD semi-quantitative analysis of phases in the desilication filter cake (wt%)

Phase	Experiment No.					
	1	2	3	4	6	
Ca ₄ Al ₂ (OH) ₁₂ CO ₂ .5H ₂ O	70	58	67	56	44	
Calcite (CaCO ₃)	21	33	11	36	31	
Portlandite [Ca(OH) ₂]	9	9	10	6	8	
Hydrogarnite Ca ₃ Al ₂ (SiO ₄) _{3-x} (OH) _{4x} [x=1.5 – 3]	0	0	12	1	18	

The existence of hydrogarnite in the desilication residue (experiments 3, 4, 6) may indicate that the simultaneous precipitation of both Si and Al is taking place, yielding the removal of two moles of Al and three moles of Si from the solution. Higher Al loss from the solution is, however, related to the crystallization of Ca₄Al₂(OH)₁₂CO₂.5H₂O.

4.3 Precipitation

Only experiments 1 and 2 produced the desired product with the preferred Al tri-hydroxides being bayerite, gibbsite and nordstrandite, and no traces of dawsonite. The XRD analysis also revealed that the products in all cases were nano-crystalline in structure. The other three experiments produced a product with a significant presence of dawsonite. In the case of experiments 3 and 4 this can perhaps be attributed to the precipitation and aging being conducted at elevated temperatures. Other studies [8] have shown that temperatures over 40°C do favour dawsonite formation. In the case of experiment 6 this perhaps can be attributed to the use of a solution with a Na₂CO₃ concentration of 80 g/l. This has also been reported to favour dawsonite formation [8]. However, in contrast solution concentrations of 100 g/l of Na₂CO₃ have been used to successfully precipitate products similar to those in experiments 1 and 2 [7]. Regardless, going forward it is recommended that all tests (carbonation and aging) be conducted with 60 g/l Na₂CO₃ concentration at temperatures less than 30 °C.

Table 10: XRD analysis of phases in the precipitation filter cake (wt%)

Phase	Experiment No.				
	1	2	3	4	6
Bayerite [α -Al(OH) ₃]	85	96	33	45	37
Gibbsite [γ -Al(OH) ₃]	12	0	0	0	0
Nordstrandite [Al(OH) ₃]	3	3	2	3	0
Dawsonite [NaAlCO ₃ (OH) ₂]	0	0	65	52	67
Natrite (Na ₂ CO ₃)	0	2	0	0	0

XRF analysis of the precipitates (Table 10) shows that the presence of critical contaminants specifically Si, Na and Ca was higher than typical industrial specifications [12]. Although the amount of SiO₂ in experiment 3 was 0.09% and an improvement from the other tests where it was 0.55%, it was still higher than the required limit of 0.015 %. The particle size distribution (PSD) analysis was only done for precipitates from experiments 1 and 2 as the others did not produce the desired products. Both products were far too fine to meet specification as 92 % > 45 μ m particle size is favoured. Future work will explore seeding the solution with product from precipitation tests 1 and 2 to help produce coarser particles through agglomeration.

Table 10: XRF analysis of major contaminants in precipitation filter cake (wt.-%) and PSD

Oxides	Industrial Specification	Experiment No.				
		1	2	3	4	6
CaO	< 0.04	0.09	0.20	0.27	0.13	0.20
SiO ₂	< 0.015	0.55	0.55	0.09	0.59	0.59
TiO ₂	< 0.004	0	0	0	0	0
Fe ₂ O ₃	< 0.015	0.01	0.03	0	0	0.02
Na ₂ O	< 0.4	0.57	3.01	19.30	21.60	13.30
PSD (median)	92 % > 45 μ m	15.97	28.91			

ICP analysis on the concentration of Al at the start and end of carbonation was conducted to determine the required time for precipitating all the Al in solution. Excluding experiment 3, because of the low concentration of Al at the start, a comparison was done between experiments 1 and 2, and 4 and 6. The starting concentration of Al in 4 and 6 is nearly double that in 1 and 2. The carbonation time in 4 and 6 was four times that of 1 and 2 but the percentage of Al precipitated is similar for both groups. It would seem that regardless of starting concentration the determining factor is the Na₂CO₃ concentration of the leaching solution. The higher the concentration the longer the carbonation time required to precipitate all the Al. Future work will evaluate the use of CO₂ with higher partial pressure or possibly pure CO₂ to reduce the carbonation time.

Table 11: Amounts of Al in solution at the start and end of precipitation tests

Experiment No.		1	2	3	4	6
Start	g/l	12.04	9.88	5.38	20.9	18.30
End	g/l	3.83	4.57	0.03	8.11	6.08
Amount precipitated	%	68.19	53.74	99.44	61.20	66.78
Carbonation time	hrs	0.5	0.5	1	2	2
Solution concentration	g/l	60	60	60	100	80

5 Conclusions

This initial test programme to evaluate the Pedersen process as a potential route to produce alumina from bauxite residue has shown there is potential in the process but a considerable amount of work still remains to be done. Although leaching with a slag containing a significant amount of gehlenite results in Al extractions no higher than 73 % the leaching is yet to be tested on slags where there is little or no gehlenite. The desilication step has shown to reduce the amount of Si in solution prior to precipitation. However, co-precipitation of Al occurs and the Si in the final product still remains higher than the industrial specification for metallurgical grade alumina. The precipitation process was the most successful amongst the three processes producing a product with the desired Al tri-hydroxides. The tests have shown that this is achieved by a combination of carbonation and aging done at temperatures lower than 30 °C on a leach solution no more than 60 g/l Na₂CO₃ concentration.

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